

TABLE 2

[Sec - amyl bromide] = 7.97×10^{-3} M[EtOH - H₂O] = 60% V/V

Experiment	Temperature (°C)	E ₁ (%)	SN ₁ (%)	$\frac{S_n}{S_n + E_1}$	$\frac{E_1}{S_n + E_1}$	k' ₁ × 10 ⁵ min ⁻¹	k' ₁ S × 10 ⁵ min ⁻¹	k' ₁ E × 10 ⁵ min ⁻¹
1	75	5.90	94.10	0.9410	0.0590	170.18	160.14	10.04
2	70	5.73	94.27	0.9427	0.0573	107.72	101.55	6.17
3	65	5.55	94.45	0.9445	0.0555	64.60	61.01	3.59
4	60	5.41	94.59	0.9459	0.0541	38.56	36.47	2.09

obtained under various physical conditions, mentioned in columns 1, 2 and 3. The increase in the velocity of first order process on addition of water to the reaction mixture is in accordance with the findings of Eliel et al⁸ and the theory of solvent action⁹. The decrease in the first order rate constant by an initial addition of potassium bromide may be attributed to the decrease in the nucleophilic activity of water molecules associated with the increase of ionic strength of the medium.

The percentage of olefin obtained in the unimolecular process (shown in column 3 of table 2) are the average of at least three observations. E₁ and SN₁ terms stand for the reactions occurring through unimolecular elimination and unimolecular substitution processes. The fractions contained in columns 5 and 6 were averages of observations taken at various intervals of time and they were almost constant which shows that these fractions actually represent the ratios in which the total unimolecular process has been rightly split up into unimolecular substitution and elimination processes. These factors of columns 5 and 6 of table 2 will give the rate constants for unimolecular substitution and elimination respectively (columns 8 and 9) on multiplication with total unimolecular rate constant (column 7). A perusal of table 2 shows that unimolecular substitution is faster than unimolecular elimination which may be attributed to predominance of inductive effect (responsible for former) over electrometric effect (responsible for latter).

The values of energy of activation for unimolecular substitution, unimolecular elimination and total unimolecular reaction come out to be 23.12, 24.57 and 22.06 kcal/mole respectively. The corresponding values of entropy of activation for above reactions have been worked out to be -15.19, -16.44 and -18.28 e.u. respectively.

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Phosphate Release from Basic Slags by EDTA

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WALLACE and coworkers¹ studied the use of metal chelates as a source of micronutrient supply to plants. Das² in a recent publication suggested the possibility of using zinc-EDTA as a combined micronutrient fertilizer and soil iron mobilizer. Of late Hajra and Chakravarti³ advocated the use of some chelating agents to release phosphate from minerals.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF BASIC SLAGS

Ingredients.	TBS	BBS	DBS	MBS	KBS	RBS
SiO ₂	14.60	15.95	27.16	20.51	25.02	33.12
FeO	28.00	10.30	5.54	9.32	10.21	0.58
MnO	3.20	4.68	5.00	9.14	10.47	2.52
CaO	32.73	41.72	36.65	43.49	39.39	33.33
MgO	6.23	6.38	6.28	9.45	11.46	6.23
Al ₂ O ₃	6.44	7.39	16.01	5.63	1.62	23.12
P ₂ O ₅	7.84	3.58	3.21	1.49	0.88	0.26
Trace elements	Zn, Cu, Mo, Co, Cr, Ni, Sn, Ti, V	Zn, Cu, Mo, Cr, Ni, Ti, V	Zn, Cu, Mo, Co, Ti, V	Zn, Cu, Mo, Co, Cr, Ni, Sn, Ti, V	Mo, Ni, Cr, Ti, V	Mo, Cr, Ni, Co, Ti, V

TABLE 2—RELEASE OF PHOSPHATE FROM BASIC SLAGS

Slag (1 g)	Initial values without EDTA		F Initial values		I After 24 hours		T After 3 days		R After 7 days	
	pH	P ₂ O ₅ %	pH	P ₂ O ₅ %	pH	P ₂ O ₅ %	pH	P ₂ O ₅ %	pH	P ₂ O ₅ %
TBS	8.05	0.0005	6.05	3.3985	6.95	3.3991	7.75	3.4005	8.00	3.4032
BBS	9.00	0.0002	7.05	1.2802	8.00	1.2804	8.80	1.2810	9.00	1.2820
DBS	8.95	0.0002	6.95	1.2505	7.85	1.2507	8.65	1.2512	8.90	1.2523
MBS	10.60	0.0001	8.65	0.4800	9.60	0.4820	10.45	0.4804	10.55	0.4809
KBS	9.10	traces	7.15	0.3798	8.05	0.3799	8.90	0.3800	9.05	0.3803
RBS	7.60	traces	5.60	0.1200	6.50	0.1202	7.30	0.1202	7.55	0.1203

TBS = Tatanagar Basic Slag
 BBS = Burnpur Basic Slag
 DBS = Durgapur Basic Slag
 MBS = Madhya Pradesh (Bhilai) Basic Slag
 KBS = Karnatak (Bhadrabati) Basic Slag
 RBS = Rourkela Basic Slag

The application of basic slags for increasing crop production has been suggested by several workers. To mention some recent advances on the subject are those of Mandal and Jha³ whose extensive researches have demonstrated the suitability of Indian basic slags for neutralizing acid soils, an essential condition for increased crop productivity. The analysis shows that the slags contain a number of micronutrient elements and phosphate besides calcium and magnesium. The present investigation is therefore designed to find out the possibility of utilizing EDTA to release phosphate from Indian basic slags.

Experimental

Basic slags from six different steel mills of India namely Burnpur, Durgapur, Tatanagar, Rourkela, Madhya Pradesh (Bhilai) and Karnatak (Bhadrabati) were powdered and sieved through a 100 mesh sieve.

The samples passing through the sieve were analysed and used in the subsequent experiments. 1 g each of different basic slags was taken in stoppered glass bottles and thoroughly treated with 100 ml distilled water. The initial pH values of the systems were recorded. Each of these samples were then thoroughly treated with 0.1 g EDTA and immediately pH values were noted. One drop of chloroform was added to each bottle with a view to suppress fungus growth.

The samples with above treatments were stirred thoroughly and incubated separately for three different lengths of time, such as 24 hours 3 days and 7 days. After the desired period of incubation the solutions were filtered and pH and P₂O₅ of the filtrates were determined. To determine P₂O₅ the filtrates were digested with a mixture of conc. H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ to break the complexed metal ions and to decompose the organic

substances. These were evaporated to dryness, brought back into solutions by adding in each case 5 ml conc. HCl, 20 ml conc. HNO₃ and 50 ml water. The solutions were again digested with 10 g NH₄NO₃ at 90° for about 10 minutes. The digested solutions were diluted and the amount of P₂O₅ in each case was estimated volumetrically after precipitating with ammonium molybdate solution⁴.

Discussion

The analysis (Table 1) shows that all the Indian basic slags contain some micronutrient elements besides calcium, magnesium and phosphorus and is suitable for healthy plant growth. The results (Table 2) indicate that the release of phosphate from basic slags by water is very little and when EDTA is used the release increases to a marked extent.

As metal chelates may be directly used as source of micronutrient supply to plants⁵, it can be concluded from this investigation that a mixture of EDTA and basic slag is very useful for supplying micronutrient elements and phosphorus to plants.

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Effective Rigid Molar Volume of Salts in Dioxane-Water Mixtures from Viscosity Data

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THE properties of aqueous electrolytic solutions are highly specific to individual ions concerned and generalisations are difficult to find. In case of viscosity, Jones-Dole¹ developed an empirical equation for the concentration dependence of viscosity of dilute electrolytic solutions, given by,

$$n_r = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (1)$$

where n_r is the relative viscosity, C is the concentration (moles/litre) and A and B are constants specific for the given solute-solvent system. This well known equation has undergone extensive investigation. Although the 'B' coefficient is empirically derived, it is

a highly specific property of the solute and can be determined by adding the individual contributions of the solute constituent ions. Thus,

$$B = z_+ B_+ + z_- B_- \quad (2)$$

Fuoss and coworkers^{2,3} working with apparent molar volume (V), obtained from the density measurements, were successful in demonstrating a like correspondence between additivity of ionic contributions to both B and V. However they were not able to confirm the Einstein⁴ equation:

$$B = 2.5 V \quad (3)$$

where 'V' is an estimation of molar volume of the solute molecules in solutions and found it valid only for large ions which can be said to resemble macroscopic particles. However, Kuruscev et al⁵, reported that the equation (3) is only valid for ions of radius $5A^\circ$. Breslau and Miller⁶ designate this 'V' as the effective rigid molar volume ' V_o ' and can be calculated as:

$$V_o = \frac{-2.5C + [(2.5C)^2 - 4(10.05 C^2)(1 - n_r)]^{1/2}}{2(10.05)C^2} \quad (4)$$

If the viscosity concentration data are available for any given salt, V_o may be obtained by the above equation and the average value is obtained. The V_o thus calculated is a fictitious or effective volume i.e. it is that volume which a mole of solute particles behave like when considered, from purely hydrodynamic reasons, as rigid macroscopic spheres. A particle which has a measure effect on neighbouring solvent molecules, from physical considerations alone, would be expected to have a higher V_o than one which has a lesser effect. Since the 'B' coefficient is an empirical measure of the ion-solvent interaction, a relation should therefore exist, with a positive slope, when 'B' is plotted against ' V_o '. From the plot the following correlations have been obtained:

$$\text{Monovalent} - B = 2.90 V_o - 0.018 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Bivalent} - B = 6.06 V_o - 0.041 \quad (6)$$

This has been extended to mixed solvents, namely dioxane-water mixtures and an attempt has been made to find the correlation of the 'B' coefficient with V_o for seventeen salts at 10, 20 and 30% dioxane-water mixtures i.e. by changing the dielectric constants. The 'B' coefficient have been taken from our own data⁷⁻¹⁰. The average V_o have been calculated by means of equation (4) and have been tabulated in table 1 along with the 'B' values. The plot of 'B' against V_o is found to be linear and the following equations are satisfied.

$$10\% \text{ Dioxane} - B = 1.33 V_o - 0.020 \quad (7)$$

$$20\% \text{ Dioxane} - B = 2.19 V_o - 0.035 \quad (8)$$

$$30\% \text{ Dioxane} - B = 3.25 V_o - 0.100 \quad (9)$$